

FINANCIAL INCLUSION AND ITS IMPACT ON THE REDUCTION OF POVERTY IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the multifaceted impact of financial inclusion on poverty reduction in Nigeria. This study employs Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to determine the efficient level of financial inclusion in Nigeria, while Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) techniques are adopted to assess the nature and strength of the relationship between financial inclusion and poverty reduction in Nigeria. This study's findings from the PCA revealed a growing level of financial inclusion in Nigeria. The ARDL findings revealed the existence of a short-run relationship among the variables. The study recommends that the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and financial service agencies provide a sound and stable monetary policy, including a reduction in lending rates that will be affordable for both rural and urban investors to access desired loans. This will widen economic activities, reduce poverty, and contribute to sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. The study also recommends continued investment in traditional banking infrastructure and the development of a digital platform to ensure widespread access to financial services across all rural areas.

Keywords: Autoregression, cointegration, unit root, financial inclusion, poverty reduction, financial access, financial usage, financial quality

JEL Code: G2, O16, E5, C32

1. INTRODUCTION

Globally, poverty remains a pervasive challenge for both developed and developing countries. According to Smith (1776), no society can surely be flourishing and happy, of which by far the greater part of the numbers are poor and miserable. The UNDP Global Multi-Dimensional Poverty Index of 2024 revealed that 1.1 billion people out of 6.3 billion live in acute multidimensional poverty, with 583 million people (over half of the population) being children under the age of 18. The index further reveals that, in Africa, especially Sub-Saharan Africa, the situation is even worse because a significant portion of the world's poor people reside in Sub-Saharan Africa and South Asian. Similarly, the UNDP Human Development Index

revealed in 2022 that, despite a wealth of natural resources in Africa, 460 million people typically fall toward the bottom of economic activities, with GDP per capita of less than \$5200 per year, with most of the population living on much less (World Bank, 2016).

In Nigeria, the 2022 Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI) survey reveals that 63% of the population (approximately 133 million people) were multidimensionally poor. The report further shows that 30.9 per cent of Nigerian's lived below the international extreme poverty line of \$2.15 per day before the outbreak of COVID-19, grappling with limited access to necessities and opportunities. According to the report, poverty and inequality are overwhelmingly bearing the brunt of economic stagnation, inflation, and structural challenges characterising Nigeria's growth trajectory among the rural population, highlighting deepening inequality and widespread economic hardship across the country. The World Bank (2025) estimated that over 54% which translates to an additional 42 million Nigerians, will be living in poverty by 2024. The report attributed the challenges to multiple economic shocks, mounting insecurity, dependence on oil, limited diversification, low job creation, vulnerability to climate shocks that impact rural agriculture, a primary source of rural livelihoods, and uncontrolled inflation.

After the 2007 global financial crisis, with the establishment of Sustainable Development Goals in 2015, adopted by all 191 United Nations member states with a specific target to combat extreme poverty in its various forms, financial inclusion discourse was more emphasized and drew more interest among scholarly and business communities. (Sahay et al., 2015). The SDGs comprise seventeen goals, including financial exclusion, ill health, illiteracy, inequality, unemployment, and the aim to ensure that everyone enjoys peace by 2030 (Adeleke & Olomola, 2022). Sahay et al. (2015) indicate that more than 60 governments across the world have set financial inclusion as a main tool for improving people's livelihoods, reducing poverty, and promoting economic development.

Despite the policy makers around the globe understanding the role of the financial system in reducing poverty and converging economic growth, in Nigeria, the 2022 National Financial Inclusion Strategy reported that 25% of Nigerians are financially excluded as of December 2023 (NFIS, 2022). In a separate study, the Enhancing Financial Inclusion Access report of 2024, revealed that financial inclusion rose to 74% in 2023 from 68% in 2020; meanwhile, 26% Nigerians are financially excluded. According to the report, despite the growth in access, certain demographic gaps continue to persist in Nigeria. For instance, the gender gap increases growth in women's financial inclusion from 60% in 2020 to 70% in 2023. The urban-rural gap decreased from 24% recorded in 2020 to 20% in 2023. Youth (18-35): 71% financial inclusion was recorded in 2023. Northern Nigeria: despite growing access, including significant gains in the North-East and North-West, all states in the North-East report exclusion levels above the national average. These individuals are predominantly farmers and dependents, more likely to be female, and tend to live in rural areas of Northern Nigeria. The challenges are due to poor access to physical banking infrastructure, digital illiteracy, low trust in formal institutions, and cumbersome identification processes (EFInA, 2024).

Several studies, like those of Osuji and Eneagwu (2024), Osuji, (2020), Dewi et al (2018), and Hicham (2017), investigated the role of financial development on poverty alleviation and income disparity in Nigeria. However, the actual impact of these efforts on the dynamics of poverty is a subject of ongoing debate and empirical investigation. Though there is a variety of literature, such as Musa, Salisu, and Magaji (2024), Mabinuor, Mathew, Bowale (2023), and Eze and Alugbuo (2021) that provide an overview of financial inclusion and poverty reduction

in Nigeria. However, none of these studies has focused on the determinants of financial inclusion, and its role in poverty reduction in Nigeria. The survey by Omenihu, Brahma, Katsika, Vrontis, Siachou, and Krasonokolakis (2024) and Adeleke and Olomola (2022) revealed an insignificant impact of financial inclusion on poverty reduction in Nigeria. The insignificant negative effect may be due to the variables and methodology used to measure financial inclusion and poverty (Abdulmumini, Dankumo & Onisawa, 2025).

While other studies like Abur (2019) and Aroyewun-Khostly and Akinola (2024) used ARDL to study financial inclusion and poverty, but primarily focused on the access dimension of financial inclusion, they often neglected the usage and quality dimension. Hannig and Jansen (2010) revealed that accessing and using a quality transaction account is a first step toward broader financial inclusion, as it allows people to store money, send and receive payments. Therefore, to fill this void and contribute to the body of knowledge, this study followed the frameworks proposed by Inyang, Eko, and Festus (2020), Cámara and Tuesta (2017), Triki and Faye (2013), Ondiege (2015), and Sethy (2016), to measure the determinants of financial inclusion using the three primary dimensions of financial access, financial usage, and financial quality to provide a comprehensive overview of the understanding of how financial inclusion interacts with poverty in the Nigerian context. The other part of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the literature review cum theoretical review; Section 3 describes the methodology; Section 4 provides detailed results and discussion of findings; and finally, Section 5 concludes the paper with policy recommendations.

2. Literature Review

2.1.1 Concept of financial inclusion

Financial inclusion, also known as inclusive financing, refers to the delivery of financial services at affordable costs to various segments of society, in contrast to financial exclusion, where these services are either unavailable or unaffordable. Financial inclusion and access to finance are different issues (GFDR, 2014). Financial inclusion means that individuals and businesses have access to and use of quality and affordable financial products and services that meet their needs (Hannig and Jansen, 2010). Financial access, according to GFDR (2014), is the ability of individuals or enterprises to obtain financial services, including credit, deposit, payment, insurance, and other risk management services. According to the report, the lack of use does not necessarily mean a lack of access. Some people may have access to financial services at affordable prices, but choose not to use certain financial services, while many others may lack access in the sense that the costs of these services are prohibitively high or that the services are simply unavailable because of regulatory barriers, legal hurdles, or an assortment of market and cultural phenomena.

Therefore, accessing and using a quality transaction account is a first step toward broader financial inclusion, as it allows people to store money, send, and receive payments. Mahendra (2006) defined financial inclusion as the availability of banking services at an affordable rate to the large segment of the vulnerable and low-income groups. He stated that although credit is the most significant component of financial services, financial inclusion covers various other services such as savings, insurance, payments, and remittance facilities issued by formal financial institutions to those perceived to be financially excluded. Meanwhile, the determinants of financial inclusion are classified into three primary dimensions of financial access, financial usage, and financial quality [Inyang, Eko, and Festus (2020), Cámara and Tuesta (2017), Triki and Faye (2013), Ondiege (2015), and Sethy (2016)].

2.1.2 Concept of Poverty

In developed countries, poverty is often viewed as either a personal or a structural issue, whereas in developing nations, the issue of poverty is more profound due to a lack of government funds (Addae-Korankye 2019). In the United States, for instance, a person is poor because of personal traits characterized by laziness, educational levels, among others, which caused the person's failure (Rank, Yoon & Hischi, 2003). Poverty, according to JRF (2013), Davis and Sanchez-Martinez (2014), and Addae-Korankye (2019), is a situation where the material resources of a person or a group of people are not adequate to meet their minimum needs. The World Bank (2004) and Davis and Sanchez-Martinez (2014) further extended the definition by indicating that poverty is characterized by pronounced deprivation in well-being, encompassing multiple dimensions. These dimensions include low incomes, the inability to acquire the basic goods and services necessary for survival with dignity, low levels of good health and education, poor access to clean water and sanitation, and inadequate capacity and opportunities to improve one's life.

2.2 Theoretical Review

This study adopted the finance-led theory by Bagehot (1873).

2.2.1 Finance-Growth Theory

It was Bagehot (1873) who first provided a detailed and modern description of how financial processes were linked to the real economy. There may have been earlier theoretical thinking before Bagehot (1873), but there is substantial evidence of 'modern' thinking on the importance of the financial system in economic growth (Stolbov, 2012). However, Bagehot's works are identified and sparked the interest of many scholars in the first half and the second half of the 20th century (Marwa & Zhanje, 2015). Patrick (1966) supported Bagehot (1873) by highlighting two ways of interweaving financial development and economic growth, named "demand-following" and "supply-leading". "Demand-following" refers to a situation in which finance is required to attract external financing, thereby supporting economic growth. "Supply-leading" occurs when financial institutions accumulate savings and transform them into investments, which are essential for the development of modern sectors of the economy.

2.3 Literature Review

The empirical evidence exists attesting to financial inclusion as having an impact on the reduction of poverty in Nigeria, as raised to achieve the objectives of the study:

Omenihu, Brahma, Katsika, Vrontis, Siachou, and Krasonokolakis (2024) investigated the financial inclusion and poverty alleviation: a critical analysis in Nigeria. The study employed PCA, OLS, and the Probit regression model to analyze the data. The result from the findings shows that financial inclusion hurts poverty, but is insignificant, while the probit result shows that age negatively correlates with financial inclusion. The study recommended that financial institutions should broaden their reach and presence in line with policy efforts targeted at promoting financial inclusion as a strategy for poverty reduction.

Aroyewun-Khostly and Akinola (2024) used ARDL to study financial inclusion and poverty in Nigeria. The findings of the study revealed a short-term and long-term negative relationship between financial inclusion and poverty. The study recommends the expansion of the Small and Medium Development Fund (MSMEDF). The study only focused on the supply side of financial inclusion while neglecting the demand and quality side.

Akande, Abdulkareem, and Olayinka (2024) employed the ARDL Bound test and VECM techniques to investigate the financial inclusion, institution quality, and poverty reduction in Nigeria. The study findings revealed a long-run relationship between poverty, financial

inclusion, and institutional quality variables. The study recommended long-run poverty alleviation strategies to sustain poverty reduction potential in Nigeria.

Musa, Salisu, and Magaji (2024) conducted an empirical analysis using SVAR to investigate the financial inclusion, poverty reduction, and economic growth in Nigeria from 1980 to 2020. The findings show that access to money has a positive impact on RGDP, while PR hurts RGDP. The study recommends that the government increase its efforts to promote financial inclusion in Nigeria. The study failed to reveal how financial inclusion impacts poverty reduction. Mabinuor, Mathew, and Bowale (2023) studied the financial inclusion and poverty reduction in Nigeria. The study employed the ARDL model to estimate the data. The result of the finding shows that financial inclusion has a major impact on the poverty index, which lowers the amount of poverty. The study recommended that CBN should develop efficient monetary policies that can have an impact on financial inclusion and poverty reduction.

Okoduwa, Kwanashie, and Ogbonna (2023) used ARDL, VAR, and Granger causality techniques to study the effect of financial development and financial inclusion on poverty reduction in Nigeria. The ARDL Bound test results showed a negative but significant impact of poverty, revealing the presence of a long-run relationship among the variables. The VAR Causality revealed a one-way direction from poverty to financial development. The study recommended the need for the banking sector to increase the volume of loans to the poor and to address constraints on credit accessibility to the poor. The variables used to capture financial development and financial inclusion did not align. Adeleke and Olomola (2022) did an empirical investigation of financial inclusion, poverty, and inequality in Nigeria. The study used VAR to analyze the data. The findings revealed that all measures of financial inclusion have no significant relationship with poverty in both the short and long run. The study recommended that the government undertake a policy intervention to provide accessible and easy-to-use financial services to the poor.

3. METHODOLOGY

To comprehensively assess the impact of financial inclusion on poverty reduction in Nigeria, this study employs a range of quantitative methodologies. The study employed Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to extract the most significant components explaining maximum variance among the variables. Variables are standardized before PCA to address scale inconsistencies, following Pineyro (2013). PCA is employed to decrease the dimensionality of the data, minimizing the number of variables and circumventing the issue of multicollinearity that arises when multiple variables are introduced (Omenihu et al., 2024). Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) is utilized to analyze the nature of the relationship between financial inclusion and poverty reduction in Nigeria.

3.1 Theoretical Framework

The study adopted the finance-growth theory by Bagehot (1873), which is the finance-induced growth nexus literature. According to the theory, the allocation channel focuses on the finance-induced efficiency gains in resource allocation that enhance growth (King and Levine, 1993). In this sense, if the loanable funds are allocated among individuals and investors, it will encourage the adoption of new technology that will boost the production process of an economy. As a result, gradually this process will spill over the whole economy (Akerlof, 1970). Gerschenkron (1962), Goldsmith (1969), Hicks (1973), Marwa & Zhanje (2015), McKinnon (1973), and Shaw (1973) have independently complemented the argument that finance widens

economic activities, increases saving and investment through interest rate manipulation, reduces poverty, and accelerates growth.

Thus, from the empirical literature, this study adopted the Osuji and Ekeagwu (2024) model that $P_t = f(Y_t)$, consequently, $P_t = f(X_t, Y_t)$ because economic growth is necessary but not sufficient to reduce poverty. Where P_t is poverty reduction, Y is economic growth, and X is other variables, including financial inclusion, that affect poverty.

3.2 Nature and Sources of Data

This research utilizes secondary annual time series data spanning from 1994 to 2023. Poverty, which is the dependent variable, is proxied by the poverty gap of less than \$3 a day sourced from the poverty gap index of 2024. Financial inclusion indicators: Data on financial access indicators—such as the number of banks, number of bank branches, number of microfinance banks, number of prime mortgage finance institutions, and number of insurance companies—were sourced from the *Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin* (CBN, 2023). Data on financial usage—such as commercial bank deposits, loans to rural areas, loans to small and medium enterprises, credit to the private sector, deposits to microfinance banks, and loans by primary mortgage finance institutions—were also sourced from CBN (2023). The data on inflation rate, real interest rates, and prime lending rates were sourced from the *World Bank Global Financial Index* (2024).

3.3 Model Specification

The model is specified in accordance with the study's objectives. The objective 1 of this study is to construct an Index for each dimension of Financial Inclusion (access, usage and quality) using Principal Component Analysis (PCA), serving as a single metric to measure the level of financial inclusion in Nigeria. The study also used the indicators of FA, FU and FQ to construct an overall financial inclusion index (FI) in Nigeria. The study follows the framework used by Omenihu et al (2024), Inyang, Eko, and Festus (2020); Goel and Sharma (2017); Yorulmaz (2017); and Sarma (2008), emphasizing that the comprehensiveness of an index depends on the dimensions it considers. Meanwhile, objective 2 of this study is within the framework of the ARDL model, aims to ascertain the strength of the relationship between financial inclusion and poverty reduction in Nigeria.

3.3.1 Model Specification for the Index of Financial Inclusion (IFI)

The models for constructing the components of IFI are specified across three dimensions. Financial Access (Supply-side indicators), 5 indicators; Financial Usage (Demand-side indicators), 6 indicators; and Financial Quality, 2 indicators.

Financial Access (FA):

$$FA = A1NB + A2NBB + A3NMFb + A4NRPMI + A5NICFA \dots\dots\dots 3.1$$

Where: NB = Number of Banks, NBB = Number of Bank Branches, NMFb = Number of Microfinance Banks, NRPMI = Number of Registered Primary Mortgage Institutions, NIC = Number of Insurance Companies

Financial Quality (FQ):

$$FQ = \pi_1RIR + \pi_2PLR \dots\dots\dots 3.2$$

Where: RIR = Real Interest Rate (%), while PLR = Prime Lending Rate (%).

Financial Usage (FU):

$$FU = \lambda_1 CBD + \lambda_2 CBLR + \lambda_3 CBLSME + \lambda_4 CBCPS + \lambda_5 DMFM + \lambda_6 LPMFFU \dots\dots 3.3$$

Where: CBD = Commercial Bank Deposit (Billions), CBLR = Commercial Bank Loan to Rural Areas (Billions), CBLSME = Commercial Bank Loans to SMEs (Billions), CBCPS = Commercial Bank Credit to Private Sector (Billions), DMFM = Deposit to Microfinance Banks (Millions), LPMF = Lending by Private Mortgage Firms (Millions).

Hence, the functional form of the IFI can be written as:

$$IFI = f(FA, FQ, FU) \dots\dots\dots 3.4$$

Where IFI = index of financial inclusion, FA = Financial Access, FU = financial quality and FQ = financial quality.

3.3.2 Model specification of ARDL

While objective 2 of this study is premised on the use of the ARDL test to examine the relationship between Poverty and financial inclusion in Nigeria. The model is specified as:

$$POV = f(FI) \dots\dots\dots 3.5$$

From equation (3.5), poverty reduction (POV) is the dependent variable while financial inclusion (FI) is the independent variable. More so, variables such as Economic Growth proxy by Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and inflation rate (IFR) have been identified as important control variables that influence the impact of financial inclusion on poverty reduction. Thus, incorporating equation (3.4) into equation (3.5), the study equation becomes:

$$POV = f(FI, GDP, IFR) \dots\dots\dots 3.6$$

Where POV=Poverty Reduction, FI=Financial Inclusion, GDP= Gross Domestic Product and IFR= Inflation Rate.

Expressing equation (3.6) in estimation form and including the constant term and the stochastic error term, equation (3.6) becomes.

$$POV = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IFI + \beta_2 GDP + \beta_3 IFR + \varepsilon_t \dots\dots\dots 3.7$$

Equation (3.7) serves as the baseline estimating model for this study and is analyzed to achieve objective two. To express equation 3.7 in the auto-regressive distributed lag (ARDL) technique, we have:

$$\Delta \ln POV_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_1 \Delta POV_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_2 \Delta \ln IFI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_3 \Delta \ln GDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_4 \Delta \ln INFL_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_5 \Delta \ln LFP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_6 \Delta \ln INFL_{t-i} + \beta_1 \ln POV_{t-1} + \beta_2 \ln IFI_{t-1} + \beta_3 \ln GDP_{t-1} + \beta_4 \ln INFL_{t-1} + \beta_5 \ln LFP_{t-1} + \beta_6 \ln INFL_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \dots\dots 3.8$$

POV = Poverty gap index less than \$3 per day, GDP = Gross Domestic Product, IFI = Index of Financial inclusion, and INFL = Inflation rate at the time *t*, while ε_t and Δ respectively the white noise error term and the difference operator. *n* is the optimal lag length included in the model, while α_i and β_i are the parameters. The inflation rate and GDP are included in this study because they are important in determining poverty reduction in Nigeria. The ARDL is utilized because it can combine variables of mixed integration order. That is, it combines variables of

integration order zero and one in the estimation process without yielding bias or spurious estimates.

4. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

This section reveals the regression results of the study using the E-View 13 statistical package. The models analyzed were interpreted to determine the extent of impact of financial inclusion on poverty reduction in Nigeria.

4.1 Financial Inclusion Index

To achieve Objective 1 of the study, this section presents the composite results of the three dimensions of financial inclusion in Nigeria from 1994 to 2023. The PCA discussion will focus on eigenvalues greater than 1, as suggested by Inyang, Eko, and Festus (2020).

Table 4.1: Financial Access (Supply side)

Eigenvalue: (Sum = 5, Average = 1)

Number	Value	Difference	Proportion	Cumulative Value	Cumulative Proportion
PCA 1	2.836015	1.431058	0.5672	2.836015	0.5672
PCA 2	1.404957	0.75989	0.2810	4.240971	0.8482
PCA 3	0.645058	0.541842	0.1290	4.886029	0.9772
PCA 4	0.103216	0.092461	0.0206	4.989245	0.9978
PCA 5	0.010755	-----	0.0022	5.00000	1.0000

Sources: Authors’ Computation using E-view 13 2025

Table 4.1 shows the PCA, with the eigenvalue of 2.836 accounting for about 57% of the total variation in the supply side of financial inclusion, while the second PCA with an eigenvalue of 1.404 accounts for about 28% of the total variation in the supply side of financial inclusion. They both account for approximately 85% of the total variation, while the 3 to 5 PCA components account for 15% of the total PCA, which is negligible. This allowed the use of PCA 1 and 2, as their eigenvalues are greater than 1.

Table 4.2: Variables Loadings/weights

Variables	PCA1	PCA2
NB	0.034585	0.619934
NBB	0.070369	-0.133584
NIC	-0.015481	-0.290298
NMFB	0.103955	0.618979
NRPMI	0.828685	-0.261663

Source: Authors' Computation Using E-views 13, 2025.

Table 4.2 presents the results for financial access (supply-side). The table reveals that in PCA1, the variable/indicator with the largest loading for the supply dimension is Number of Registered Primary Mortgage Institutions (NRPMI) with a weight of 0.828685. The second largest is the Number of Finance Banks with a weight of 0.103955. The third position is taken by the Number of bank branches (NBB) with a weight of 0.070369. The fourth is the number

of banks with a weight of 0.034585. The last is the Number of Insurance Companies with a negative weight of -0.015481. The positive sign of the results implies that their supplies are enough to meet the populations that are willing to access financial services in Nigeria. The number of insurance companies occupies a negative probability because the insurance companies are located only in the urban areas of the 36 states in the country. This result goes in tandem with other studies that report that the insurance companies in Nigeria are insufficient for supplying the needed services in the country.

Table 4.3: Financial Usage (Demand side)

Eigenvalue: (Sum = 6, Average = 1)

Number	Value	Difference	Proportion	Cumulative Value	Cumulative Proportion
PCA 1	3.399174	1.862538	0.5665	3.399174	0.5665
PCA 2	1.536636	0.775227	0.2561	4.935811	0.8226
PCA 3	0.761410	0.533175	0.1269	5.697220	0.9495
PCA 4	0.228235	0.163993	0.0380	5.925455	0.9876
PCA 5	0.064241	0.053938	0.0107	5.989697	0.9983
PCA 6	0.010303	-----	0.0017	6.000000	1.0000

Sources: Authors’ Computation using E-view 13 2025

Table 4.3 shows that the PCA with the eigenvalue of 3.399 accounts for about 57% of the total variation in the demand side of financial inclusion, while the second PCA with an eigenvalue of 1.537 accounts for about 25% of the total variation in the demand side of financial inclusion. They both account for about 82% of total variation, while the 4 to 6 PCA accounts for only 18% of the total PCA, which is negligible and allows the use of PCA 1 and 2 that whose eigenvalues are greater than 1.

Table 4.4: variables Loadings/weights

Variable	PCA1	PCA2
CBDR_B_	0.407209	0.532592
CBLP_B_	0.491138	-0.064910
CBLR_B_	-0.031856	-0.077735
CBLS_B_	-0.421671	-0.056948
DMFB_M_	0.609982	-0.557296
LPMF_B_	0.205097	0.626313

Source: Authors' Computation Using E-views 13, 2025.

Table 4.4 is the PCA results, which reveal the loadings for the demand dimension indicators (financial usage). The result shows that Deposits in Microfinance Banks have the highest weight of 0.609982, followed by Commercial Bank loans to the Private Sector with a weight of 0.491138, Commercial Bank deposits in rural areas, 0.407209 and then Loans in Private Mortgage finance, which is 0.205097. While Commercial Bank Loans to Small and Medium

Enterprises and Commercial Bank Branch Loans in Rural Areas have the lowest and negative loadings results of -0.421671 and -0.031856, respectively. The results imply that indicators representing demand for services for deposit to microfinance banks, loan to the private sector (Household, Individuals & Firms), Mortgage services, Commercial Bank Deposits by rural area, are services offered in most urban areas, leading the category of financial services in high demand.

The result implies that the demand for financial services is greater than their supply in Nigeria. While the results for the commercial bank deposit in rural areas show that demand for financial services in rural areas is only needed for deposit purposes.

Table 4.5: Financial Quality

Eigenvalue: (Sum = 2, Average = 1)

Number	Value	Difference	Proportion	Cumulative Value	Cumulative Proportion
PCA 1	1.230521	0.461042	0.6153	1.230521	0.6153
PCA 2	0.769479	-----	0.3847	2.000000	1.0000

Sources: Authors’ Computation using E-view 13 2025

Table 4.5 shows that it's only PCA 1 with the eigenvalue of 1.231 that accounts for about 61% of the total variation in the regulation side of financial inclusion; therefore, PCA 1, which has an eigenvalue greater than 1, will be used.

Table 4.6: variable Loadings/weights

Variables	PCA 1
RIR	-0.707107
PLR	0.707107

Source: Authors' Computation Using E-views 13, 2025.

Table 4.6 reveals a price barrier (financial quality) in two indicators: the real interest rate and the prime lending rate. The real interest rate result of -0.71 indicates how the interest rate negatively affects both the supply and the demand of financial services in Nigeria. The lack of sufficient data greatly hampers the quality dimension, as only indicators representing the price barrier are available.

Table 4.7: Index of Financial Inclusion

Eigenvalue: (Sum = 3, Average = 1)

Number	Value	Difference	Proportion	Cumulative Value	Cumulative Proportion
PCA 1	2.135375	1.468614	0.7118	2.135375	0.7118
PCA 2	0.666760	0.468895	0.2223	2.802135	0.9340
PCA 2	0.197865	-----	0.0660	3.000000	1.0000

Sources: Authors’ Computation using E-view 13 2025

Table 4.7 shows that it's only PCA 1 with the eigenvalue of 2.135 that accounts for about 71% of the total variation of the financial inclusion index, while PCA2 and PCA3 with 0.667 and 0.198 of eigenvalue, respectively, account for only 29%. Therefore, PCA 1, which has an eigenvalue greater than 1, will be used.

Table 4.8: variables Loadings/weights

Variables	PCA 1
FA	0.633258
FQ	-0.231716
FU	0.738443

Source: Authors' Computation Using E-views 13, 2025.

Table 4.8 shows the results of the financial inclusion index. The results indicate that in PCA1, the demand-side dimension has the highest loading, with a weight of 0.738443, followed by the supply-side dimension, with a weight of 0.633258. This suggests that demand for financial services is slightly above the supply for financial services in Nigeria; this is in line with the study of Sethy (2016), which found high financial inclusion on case of demand side but low financial inclusion on case of supply side in India. The financial quality possesses a negative weight of only -0.231716, which could be due to the price factors (inverse relationship) that affect the contribution of Financial Inclusion in Nigeria.

4.2 ARDL Bound Test Result

The study performs some vital preliminary tests meant to direct and authenticate the choice of estimation techniques employed to address the objectives of the study.

4.2.1 ADF Unit Root Test

This study used the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) to examine the stationarity attributes of the variables because it is considered superior due to its popularity, ease and wide application. In practice, if the ADF value is less than its critical value shows that the underlying series is non-stationary, and the null hypothesis is not rejected. However, when an ADF value is greater than its critical value shows that the underlying series is stationary, and the null hypothesis is rejected. Table 4.9 below reveals the ADF result:

Table 4.9: Unit Root Test (ADF)

Variables	Level	Prob.	First diff	Prob.	Order of Integration	Remarks
POVT	-2.48	0.4452	-5.3541	0.0009	1(1)	Significant
IFI	-5.05	0.0092	-5.5629	0.0058***	1(1)	Significant
GDP	6.14	1.0000	-0.8888	0.9434	1(1)	Insignificant
INFL	-46.3	0.0000	-2.5671	0.2967	1(0)	Significant

Source: Authors' Computation using E-view 13, 2025. Note that* ** and * signify statistically significant at 10% 5% and 1% respectively.**

The unit root results of ADF tests are presented in Table 4.9. ADF demonstrated that the series are mixed stationary at the level and first difference, or the series contains a unit root. From ADF, the IFI and INFL are stationary at level I(0), POVT is stationary at first difference I(1), while the GDP is not significant. The condition of the mixed stationary data of at level I(0) and at first difference I(1) series permitted this study to estimate the data using the ARDL model of estimation.

4.2.2 Bounds Test Co-integration Result (Objective 2)

The long-run relationship between economic growth, financial inclusion, gross capital formation, foreign direct investment, total labour productivity rate, and inflation rate was investigated using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds cointegration test. Table 4.10 reports the results of the cointegration test:

Table 4.10: Cointegration Test Result

F-Statistic	K
2.141296	3
Critical Bounds	
Significance level	1(0) 1(1)
10%	3.77 4.53
5%	4.54 5.42
1%	6.43 7.53

Source: Authors' Computation using E-views 13, 2025.

The ARDL bounds cointegration test has the following null and alternative hypotheses. There is no cointegration between the dependent and the independent variables, and there is cointegration between the dependent and the independent variables. The null hypothesis is rejected if the F-statistic of the test is greater than the upper critical bound at a given significance level. From Table 4.10, it is observed that the F-statistic of 2.141296 is lower than the lower and upper critical bounds at 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels. The study, therefore, accepted the null hypothesis that there is cointegration between the dependent and independent variables. With this result, the study concluded that there is no long-term relationship between poverty, financial inclusion, economic growth, and the inflation rate.

4.2.3 Long and Short Run ARDL Results

This study employed the ARDL technique to estimate the model expressing the relationship between poverty reduction, financial inclusion, GDP and inflation rate and the result is reported in Table 4.11:

Table 4.11: Long and Short Run ARDL Results

LONG RUN				
Variables	Coefficient	St.error	t-statistics	prob
Constant	38.10150	11.31871	3.366239	0.0042
@TREND	-0.436997	0.270155	-1.617577	0.1266
POVT (-1)	0.383553	0.205301	1.868252	0.0814
IFI	-1.172286	1.110438	-1.055697	0.3078
GDP__B_	0.000415	0.002207	2.005702	0.0633
GDP__B_ (-1)	-0.001228	0.000383	-3.207494	0.0057
GDP__B_ (-2)	0.000769	0.000258	2.989320	0.0093
INFL	0.225909	0.170262	1.3268626	0.2044
INFR (-1)	-0.203232	0.084379	-2.408564	0.0293

Source: Authors' computation using E-views 13, 2025.

R-squared	0.970777	Mean Dependent var	45.83333
Adjusted R2	0.955191	SD Dependent var	10.76074
F-Statistics	62.28626	Akaike Information Criterion	4.764336
Prob(F-statistic)	0.00000	Schwarz criterion	5.206106
Durbin Watson	2.893197	Hannan Quinn Criteria	4.881538

Table 4.11 shows that the coefficient of the constant is 38.10150, implying that, holding other variables constant, POVT will increase by 38.10150. The result is associated with a probability value of 0.0042, indicating its significance at the 5% level of significance.

The coefficient of POVT revealed a positive value of 0.383553, indicating that, *ceteris paribus*, a 1% increase in POVT will lead to a decrease of 0.383553%. However, its p-value of 0.0814 indicates a significant result at the 10% level of significance.

The coefficient IFI is -1.172286; the results revealed that, *ceteris paribus*, a 1% increase in IFI will result in a 1.172286% decrease in POVT in the current year. The result is associated with a probability of 0.3078, indicating significance at all levels of significance.

The coefficient of the GDP in the current year is 0.000415, which implies that, *ceteris paribus*, a 1% increase in GDP will lead to a rise in POVT by 0.000415%. However, its probability value of 0.0633 indicates a significant result at the 10% level of significance. Meanwhile, the short-run results for the first and second lags are -0.001228 and 0.000769. They show that, *ceteris paribus*, a 1% increase in GDP leads to a decrease in POVT by 0.001228 and an increase of 0.000769%. However, the probability values of 0.0059 and 0.0093 indicate a significant result at the 5% level of significance, respectively, for the first and second lags.

The coefficient of INFL in the long run is 0.225909. The results show that, *ceteris paribus*, a 1% increase in inflation leads to a rise in poverty by 0.225909%. However, the associated probability value of 0.2044 shows an insignificant result at the 5% level of significance. While the coefficient of INFL in lag 1 reveals itself to be -0.203232. The results show that *ceteris paribus*, a 1% increase in INFL will initiate a decrease of POVT by 0.203232 in the first lag. However, its associated probability values of 0.0293 show significance at the 10% level of significance.

4. 3 Discussion of the Findings

The study employed the use of Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test results in Table 4.5, which revealed that the majority of the variables result in a mixture of I(0) and I(1) order of integration. As a result of the preliminary tests, the ARDL Bounds test is performed to ascertain the long-run relationship among the variables selected.

The first model is designed to measure the level of financial inclusion in Nigeria. Applying the PCA method, the IFI is 2.566097 as of 2020. The result implies an increasing level of financial inclusion in Nigeria, which aligns with the studies of Thai-Ha and Farhad (2019) and Kim, Yu, and Hassan (2018), which revealed that growing financial inclusion favours financial sustainability and tends to reduce poverty. Additionally, the coefficients of the financial inclusion index are negative in both the long run and the current lag of the ARDL Bound, indicating that an increase in the index leads to a significant reduction in the poverty level and expansion of economic activities in Nigeria. This finding aligns with the studies of Aroyewun-Khosty and Akinola (2024), Osuji and Ekeagwu (2024), and Abdulmumini, Dankumo, and Onisanwa (2025), which suggest that the development of financial sectors tends to expand economic activities and reduce poverty. The ARDL model result reveals the absence of long-run cointegration among the variables. The result is confirmed with the study of De Hann et al (2022), Hicham (2017), and Dandume (2014) that financial development does not have a direct effect on poverty reduction, questioning the claims by Cihal et al (2012) that economies with higher levels of financial development grow faster and experience faster reductions in poverty levels.

Diagnostic Test

To assess the robustness of the models, the structural stability test of the parameter on the axis, as well as the cumulative sum of recursive residuals (CUSUM) and cumulative sum of recursive residuals squares (CUSUMSQ), are applied. The graphical representation of the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ approaches shows that the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ remain within the boundaries throughout the period, as indicated by the blue lines lying between the red lines. However, the parameters of long-run estimates converging to zero mean in the long run suggest that models are dynamically stable and consistent.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study investigates the impact of financial inclusion on poverty reduction in Nigeria. The study's findings indicate that access to financial services, particularly through the expansion of commercial bank branches and the introduction of digital financial services, can have a positive impact on economic growth and reduce poverty. Although the study of Omenihu et al (2024) and Adeleke and Olomola (2022) suggest that there is an insignificant direct relationship between financial inclusion measures and poverty reduction, highlighting that the effects may not be immediate or straightforward. Thus, this study concludes that the use of financial services efficiently and effectively channelling funds to the appropriate investors tends to expand economic activities and reduce miserable poverty. This is because Onaolopo (2015), Dauda, Abubakar and Abdullahi (2020), Joseph, Tella, Dan'Asabe and Mustapha (2023) and Obiakor (2024) found that financial activities have a significant influence on poverty reduction and attainment of inclusive growth.

Therefore, for Nigeria to harness the full potential of financial inclusion in its fight against poverty, the Central Bank of Nigeria, through its monetary policy, should expand the services of financial institutions (most especially the commercial bank branches and insurance services) through the advent of digital financial services in rural areas, which can positively reduce poverty and influence economic growth. The study also recommends that the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and financial service agencies provide a sound and stable monetary policy, including a reduction in lending rates that will be affordable for both rural and urban investors to access desired loans. This will widen economic activities, reduce poverty, and contribute to sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. The study also recommends that the government continue to invest in traditional banking infrastructure (power, energy, road network, and telecommunications) and develop a digital platform to ensure widespread access to financial services and participation, as this will widen economic activities and reduce the poverty rate in Nigeria.

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